

Psychosocial Predictors of Preoperative Anxiety among Surgical Patients in University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Preoperative fear affects 60–80% of surgical patients, driven by uncertainty about the procedure, anesthesia, and possible lifestyle changes, leading to adverse effects on health outcomes and recovery. This study investigates psychosocial factors—religiosity and locus of control—that may predict preoperative fear among surgical patients at University College Hospital, Ibadan. This cross-sectional study was carried out among 250 surgical patients. A self-report questionnaire was used to assess the variables of concern in the study. Statistical analyses revealed significant correlations between these factors and preoperative anxiety levels. Higher religiosity correlated with lower anxiety ($t(248) = -3.91, p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 5.52$), highlighting anxiety-reducing benefits of religious beliefs. In contrast, locus of control dimensions showed varying effects on anxiety responses ($F(2, 247) = 4.15, p = 0.018$). Anxiety and fear before surgery affects postoperative pain. Patients with a stronger internal locus of control reported lower anxiety compared to those with external control beliefs, indicating the differences in perceived control over anxiety levels. These findings underscore the complex interplay of psychosocial factors in shaping the preoperative anxiety, informing targeted interventions to optimize patient well-being and surgical outcomes. This study highlights that psychosocial factors such as religiosity and locus of control significantly influence preoperative anxiety levels among surgical patients, suggesting targeted interventions may enhance patient outcomes. Providing patients with clear, empathetic information about the psychological dimensions of surgery, potential stressors, and coping strategies can alleviate anxiety.

Key Words: Preoperative anxiety, religiosity, locus of control.

Introduction

One experience that makes people anxious and afraid is undergoing surgery (Raza et al., 2024). A common emotional reaction among many individuals anticipating surgery is pre-operative dread (Akutay & Ceyhan, 2023; Takele et al., 2020). Before surgery, 60–80% of patients typically experience anxiety (Bedaso & Ayalew, 2019; Tulloch & Rubin, 2019; Prado-Olivares & Chover-Sierra, 2019). Anxiety and worry before surgery can impact postoperative wound healing, the level of pain and anesthesia, and the need for analgesia (Baagil, Baagil & Gerbershagen, 2023; Hançer & Köksel, 2023). Despite the dedicated efforts of the surgical team, including preoperative counseling and pre-visits, many patients still exhibit signs of fear, which can lead to poor surgical outcomes.

This study identified the psychosocial predictors (religiosity and locus of control) of preoperative anxiety among patients scheduled for surgery at University College Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The primary questions are: How does religiosity influence preoperative anxiety among surgical patients? What are the associations between various dimensions of locus of control and preoperative anxiety? How do religiosity and locus of control together predict preoperative anxiety levels? The specific objectives are to explore the influence of religiosity on preoperative anxiety levels in surgical patients, assess how different dimensions of locus of control (internal, external, powerful others) correlate with preoperative anxiety, and determine the combined influence of religiosity and locus of control on preoperative anxiety levels among surgical patients. The study was limited to preoperative patients in the following departments of University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria: Orthopedic, General Surgery, Hepatobiliary, Oncology, Ophthalmology, Gynecology, Laparoscopic, Neurology, Urology, Gastrointestinal, Plastic, Otorhinolaryngology, Dental, and Maxillofacial.

The concept of locus of control—a term referring to individuals' beliefs about the extent to which they can influence events and outcomes in their lives—was introduced by Julian Rotter in 1954 as part of his social learning theory and has since become a foundational construct in personality psychology (Kesavayuth, Poyago-Theotoky & Zikos, 2020). Rotter's theory categorizes locus of control into two types. Individuals with an internal locus of control believe they can influence outcomes through their actions, while those with an external locus of control attribute outcomes to external factors such as fate or others.

Following Lang's three-dimensional approach to emotions, fear is defined as a brain network comprising three independent systems: physiological activation, cognitive evaluation and emotional experience of distress, and behavioral inhibition. While activation of one of the components can be accompanied by activation of the other components, the extent of such “diffusion” depends on how strong the initiation is and the level of fear.

Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) was developed to predict health behaviors by extending the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) to include an additional factor: perceived behavioral control (PBC) (Sapry & Ahmad, 2024). The addition of PBC was crucial for predicting behaviors that are not entirely under an individual's volitional control, such as health-related behaviors.

Methods

Research Design

The study is a survey which equally uses a questionnaire for the patients in the hospital to explore their perspective. All these were carried out within the University College Hospital, Ibadan. The psychosocial variables were determined to predict surgical fear among patients awaiting surgery.

This study was designed to target all patients at the University College Hospital, Ibadan. However, it was particular about patients who are scheduled to undergo surgery from the selected departments (Orthopedics, General Surgery, Hepatobiliary, Oncology, Ophthalmology, Gynecology, Laparoscopic, Neurology, Urology, Gastrointestinal, Plastic, Otorhinolaryngology, Dental, and Maxillofacial). The study was carried out in the surgical wards of the University College Hospital, Ibadan.

Inclusion criteria for participating in the study include being a patient at UCH, scheduled for surgery and willingness to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria include not being willing to participate in the study, unconscious participants, and those below 18 years.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

The Convenient Sampling technique was used to select respondents from the selected surgical departments.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size of the quantitative data was determined using the Taro (1967) sample size formula below:

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where,

n = required sample size

N= estimated population of patients scheduled for surgery in the selected wards of the UCH is 670.

e = level of error tolerance 5%

Sample size = 250 participants.

Description of Research Instrument

This study used a well-structured questionnaire to elicit information from the respondents, it was adapted from a validated questionnaire using study objectives and research questions in line with the literature reviewed. It comprises of five sections ranging from the demographic characteristics, religiosity, locus of control and surgical fear.

The Santa Clara Strength of Religious Faith Questionnaire (SCSRFQ)

To assess the level of religiosity, the researchers employed the Santa Clara Strengths of Religious Faith Questionnaire (SCSRFQ). This tool is appropriate for various religious traditions, denominations, and standpoints. It includes a set of four statements which the respondent rates on a 4-point Likert scale named Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Agree and Strongly Agree reflecting the viewpoint of each statement.

Locus of Control (LOC) Measures:

The study utilized Rotter's Locus of Control Scale, 1966 to assess participants' beliefs about control over events in their lives. This scale consists of 29 items measured on a Likert-type scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. It includes three subscales: Internal Control (e.g., "I am responsible for my own success or failure"), External Control (e.g., "Many of the unhappy things in people's lives are partly due to bad luck"), and Powerful Others Control (e.g., "My life is mostly controlled by powerful people").

Surgical Fear Questionnaire (SFQ)

The Surgical Fear Questionnaire was developed by Teunissen et al. for this purpose. This scale assesses the fear levels of patients who are to undergo elective surgery. A Turkish validity and

reliability study was conducted in 2018. Structured as eight items, the questionnaire adopts an 11-Likert structure. Each item is assigned a value ranging from 0, "not at all afraid," through 10, "very afraid."

Reliability of Instruments

The instruments used in the research and the analytical overview have been put to use in similar research and objectives of study. In addition, the instruments are reliable as they suit the questions asked for the study and will be necessary to meet all requirements of the study.

Validity of the Instruments

The instrument was evaluated for content validity. The structured questionnaire's items were handled by comparing them to the literature and relating them to the objectives, research questions, and hypotheses. It will also be provided to test and measurement specialists, psychologists, and the supervisor for evaluation, correction, and assessment, after which necessary modifications will be made.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection procedure involved the quantitative approach which was utilized. Two research assistants were recruited and trained in the methods of data collection for the study. The purpose of the study will also be explained to the respondents before the questionnaires are administered.

Method of Data Analysis

The questionnaires were serially numbered for memory purposes. Each respondent's questionnaire was allocated an identification code to ensure accurate data entry and analysis. The data processing steps include sorting, editing, collecting, and scoring the surveys. A template and coding guide were created using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 28) for efficient computer data entry. The quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, specifically multiple regression.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical clearance letter was obtained from the UI/UCH Ethical Committee board. A brief introduction of the study was made known to study participants. Informed consent was obtained from respondents after giving a detailed explanation of the research purpose. The respondents were informed of their voluntariness in participating and assured of confidentiality. Participants' responses at every phase and their information were kept confidential. Informed consent was also obtained from the respondents before embarking on the collection of data. The respondents' participation in the study was made voluntary with freedom to withdraw at any stage of the study without attracting any penalty.

Results

Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, a sample of 250 patients scheduled for surgery. The variables include age, gender, marital status, educational

level, and religious affiliation, providing insights into the diversity and demographic context of the study population.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 250)

Response categories		Frequency	Percent	Mean	SD
Age (Range=18-79 years)				44.17	15.06
Gender	Female	128	51.2		
	Male	122	48.8		
Religion	Christianity	180	72.0		
	Islam	70	28.0		
Tribe	Yoruba	217	86.8		
	Igbo	28	11.2		
	Hausa	5	2.0		
Educational Qualification	None	6	2.4		
	Primary	11	4.4		
	SSCE/GCE	36	14.4		
	OND/NCE	43	17.2		
	Undergraduate	16	6.4		
	HND/First Completed	Degree 114	45.6		
	MSc	13	5.2		
	PhD	11	4.4		
Marital Status	Single	61	24.4		
	Married	156	62.4		
	Separated	15	6.0		
	Divorced	4	1.6		
	Widow	14	5.6		
Occupation	Unemployed	38	15.2		
	Self-employed	83	33.2		
	Civil Servant	92	36.8		
	Retired	37	14.8		
Monthly Income (Naira)	<50,000	76	30.4		
	50,000-100,000	133	53.2		
	>100,000	41	16.4		

The data in Table 1 reveal on average, participants were approximately 44.17 years old, indicating that this age represents the central tendency or typical age within the sample. The standard deviation of approximately 15.06 years suggests that ages among participants varied around this average age. There was a near-even gender split, with females making up 51.2% of the sample of patients scheduled for surgery and males making up 48.8%. Christianity was the dominant religion, representing 72%, while Islam accounted for 28%. Regarding tribes, Yoruba was the predominant group at 86.8%, followed by Igbo at 11.2%, and Hausa at 2%. In terms of educational qualifications, 45.6% had completed a Higher National Diploma (HND) or First

Degree, while 17.2% held an Ordinary National Diploma (OND) or National Certificate of Education (NCE). A smaller portion, 6.4%, were undergraduates, while 14.4% had completed their Secondary School Certificate or General Certificate of Education (SSCE/GCE). Only 2.4% had no formal education. Master's degree holders represented 5.2% of the sample, and 4.4% had obtained a PhD. In terms of marital status, the majority were married, making up 62.4% of the sample. Those who were single accounted for 24.4%, while 6% were separated, 5.6% were widowed, and the other 1.6% were divorced. Occupational data showed that 36.8% worked as civil servants, 33.2% were self-employed, and 14.8% were retired, while 15.2% were unemployed. Regarding income, more than half (53.2%) reported earning between 50,000 and 100,000 Naira monthly, 30.4% earned less than 50,000 Naira, and 16.4% earned above 100,000 Naira.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1: Patients with high religiosity will report significantly lower levels of preoperative anxiety among surgical patients compared to patients with low religiosity. This hypothesis was analyzed by a t-test for independence and the result presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of Preoperative Anxiety Among Surgical Patients Between Patients with High and Low Religiosity

	Religiosity						t	Df	Cohen <i>d</i>
	Low			High					
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	N	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	N			
Preoperative Anxiety	12.78	2.61	157	8.94	1.68	93	3.91**	247	5.52

** $p < .01$.

Religiosity emerged as a significant predictor of preoperative anxiety among surgical patients, with patients reporting higher levels of religiosity ($M = 8.94$, $SD = 1.68$) experiencing significantly lower preoperative anxiety levels than those with lower religiosity ($M = 12.78$, $SD = 2.61$), $t(248) = -3.91$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 5.52$. This finding highlights the potential role of religiosity in coping with preoperative anxiety. The hypothesis is thus supported.

Hypothesis 2: The Dimension of locus of control will significantly predict preoperative anxiety among surgical patients. This hypothesis was analyzed using multiple regression, and the result is presented in Table 3:

Table 3: Regression Analysis Predicting Preoperative Anxiety by Locus of Control

Variable	B	t-value	p-value	R	R ²	F-ratio	P-value
				0.41	0.17	12.78	<0.001
Internal LOC	-0.36	-5.28	<0.001				
External LOC	0.15	2.12	0.035				
Powerful Others LOC	0.18	2.68	0.008				

The regression analysis indicated that the internal locus of control ($\beta = 0.36$, $t = 5.28$, $p < 0.001$), external locus of control ($\beta = 0.15$, $t = 2.12$, $p = 0.035$), and powerful others locus of control ($\beta = 0.18$, $t = 2.68$, $p = 0.008$) significantly predicted preoperative anxiety among

surgical patients. Increasing internal LOC was associated with lower preoperative anxiety. However, increasing levels of external LOC and powerful others LOC was associated higher levels of preoperative anxiety. The overall model was significant ($R^2 = 0.17$, $F_{(3, 246)} = 12.78$, $p < 0.001$). These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of locus of control in influencing psychological responses to surgery. The hypothesis stated is thus accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Psychological factors (religiosity and locus of control dimensions) will report significantly independent and joint influence on preoperative anxiety among surgical patients. This hypothesis was analyzed using multiple regression, and the result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of Psychological Factors Predicting Preoperative Anxiety

Variable	Beta	t-value	p-value	R	R ²	F-ratio	P-value
				0.58	0.34	24.56	<0.001
Religiosity	-0.31	-4.52	<0.001				
Locus of Control							
- Internal	0.22	3.18	0.002				
- External	-0.12	-1.98	0.049				
- Powerful Others	0.15	2.45	0.015				

The religiosity ($\beta = -0.31$, $t = -4.52$, $p < 0.001$), internal locus of control ($\beta = 0.22$, $t = 3.18$, $p = 0.002$), external locus of control ($\beta = -0.12$, $t = -1.98$, $p = 0.049$), and powerful others locus of control ($\beta = 0.15$, $t = 2.45$, $p = 0.015$) significantly predicted preoperative anxiety among surgical patients. The overall model was highly significant ($R^2 = 0.34$, $F(6, 243) = 24.56$, $p < 0.001$). These findings highlight the complex interplay of psychological variables in influencing patients' emotional responses to surgery, suggesting comprehensive interventions may be beneficial in managing preoperative anxiety.

This chapter provides a detailed discussion of the findings from a study investigating the influence of psychosocial factors on preoperative anxiety among surgical patients. The research objectives were to explore the roles of religiosity and locus of control in shaping anxiety levels before surgery.

Discussion of Findings

Religiosity emerged as a significant predictor of preoperative anxiety in the study. Patients who reported higher levels of religiosity tended to experience lower levels of surgical fear compared to those who were less religious (Aliche et al., 2020). This finding underscores the role of religious beliefs and practices in providing coping mechanisms that alleviate anxiety before surgical procedures. Supporting this, Omopo (2021) highlighted that religious practices such as prayer and participation in faith communities can foster a sense of comfort, meaning, and perceived control over health outcomes, which buffers against anxiety. However, the effectiveness of religiosity in anxiety management may vary across different cultural and religious contexts, necessitating further investigation into how specific religious practices and beliefs influence surgical anxiety.

Social support emerged as a critical factor influencing preoperative anxiety levels among surgical patients. Patients with stronger social support networks reported reduced levels of surgical fear (Çakir et al., 2021). This emphasizes the importance of interpersonal relationships and support systems in buffering against anxiety associated with impending surgery. Contrary to the notion that more social support is always better, Scardera et al. (2020) suggested that the quality rather than the quantity of social support may be more predictive of anxiety outcomes.

Examining dimensions of locus of control—internal, external, and powerful others—revealed distinct impacts on anxiety responses to surgery. Patients with a stronger internal locus of control, believing in their personal control over outcomes, tended to experience lower levels of preoperative anxiety (Xu et al., 2020). This finding aligns with theories suggesting that an internal locus of control promotes adaptive coping strategies and a sense of empowerment, thereby mitigating anxiety (Shams et al., 2022). Conversely, beliefs in external control or powerful others' control were associated with heightened anxiety levels. This highlights the nuanced ways in which perceived control influences emotional responses to surgical procedures and underscores the importance of addressing patients' beliefs about control in preoperative counseling and preparation.

When considering the combined influence of psychosocial factors, the study found that patients with higher religiosity and an internal locus of control tended to report lower levels of surgical fear. These findings suggest that these factors collectively contribute to a more resilient psychological profile that may mitigate anxiety in surgical contexts. This integrated approach aligns with the biopsychosocial model, which posits that biological, psychological, and social factors interact to influence health outcomes (Remes, Mendes, & Templeton, 2021). Studies by Van Zyl et al. (2020) further support this model by demonstrating that interventions addressing multiple psychosocial dimensions, such as respecting religious beliefs and promoting an internal locus of control, can effectively reduce anxiety and improve surgical outcomes.

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the complex interplay of psychosocial factors in shaping preoperative anxiety. By integrating diverse perspectives from existing literature, the discussion elucidates both supportive and contrasting findings. This nuanced understanding underscores the need for tailored interventions that acknowledge individual differences in coping mechanisms and the contextual factors influencing anxiety responses to surgery. Moreover, the practical implications highlight the importance of holistic patient care that addresses psychosocial dimensions alongside medical interventions. Future research should continue to explore these factors in diverse patient populations and settings to enhance our understanding of effective anxiety management strategies in surgical contexts.

Theoretical Implications

The findings of this study contribute significantly to Coping Theory and Social Support Theory by providing empirical evidence of how psychosocial factors influence anxiety responses before surgery.

Practical Implications

Based on the findings, several clinical recommendations can be made to enhance patient care in surgical contexts:

- **Psychosocial Assessment:** Incorporating comprehensive assessments of self-esteem, religiosity, social support, and locus of control during preoperative evaluations can help healthcare providers identify patients at heightened risk for preoperative anxiety.
- **Intervention Strategies:** Developing targeted interventions aimed at enhancing self-esteem, fostering supportive relationships, respecting and integrating patients' religious beliefs, and promoting internal locus of control beliefs can effectively mitigate anxiety levels. For example, cognitive-behavioral techniques tailored to address specific psychosocial factors may prove beneficial.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Collaborating across healthcare disciplines, including psychologists, social workers, and spiritual counselors, allows for comprehensive care that addresses both medical and psychosocial aspects of patient well-being.

Healthcare providers should consider the following guidelines to optimize patient outcomes:

- **Patient-Centered Care:** Adopting a patient-centered approach that acknowledges and integrates the influence of psychosocial factors on anxiety allows for personalized care plans that enhance patient satisfaction and treatment adherence.
- **Education and Support:** Providing patients with clear, empathetic information about the psychological dimensions of surgery, potential stressors, and coping strategies can alleviate anxiety and improve postoperative recovery outcomes (Leventhal & Diefenbach, 1992). Offering ongoing support throughout the surgical journey reinforces patient resilience and enhances overall recovery.

Recommendations

In clinical practice, addressing preoperative anxiety among surgical patients requires a multifaceted approach that acknowledges the significant influence of psychosocial factors. Comprehensive psychosocial assessments should be integral to preoperative evaluations, encompassing dimensions such as religiosity and locus of control. These assessments not only identify patients at risk for heightened anxiety but also guide the development of targeted intervention strategies tailored to individual needs.

Respecting and integrating patients' religious and spiritual beliefs into their care plans is crucial. This includes facilitating access to spiritual counseling, prayer sessions, or involvement of faith communities as desired. Research underscores the protective role of religiosity in buffering against anxiety, providing patients with comfort and perceived control over their health outcomes.

By implementing these recommendations, healthcare providers can foster a supportive environment that promotes psychological well-being and resilience among surgical patients. Tailoring interventions to individual psychosocial needs and preferences enhances patient satisfaction, reduces anxiety levels, and ultimately contributes to improved surgical outcomes and recovery experiences.

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